

Book(s) of Daniel

also known as “Book of Daniel”, “Danielic Literature”, “Danielic Traditions”

By Megan Remington, UCLA

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The book(s) of Daniel depict a complex set of texts and traditions revolving around the figure Daniel, a Judean youth in the imperial courts following the Babylonian Exile (586 BCE). The earliest texts were composed in different languages (Aramaic, Greek, and Hebrew) and later preserved in distinct versions (Old Greek, Masoretic text, fragments from Qumran, and the Greek Theodotion). The texts also feature different genres, such as narrative court-tales set in the Babylonian, Median, and Persian imperial courts, as well as revelatory or apocalyptic visions. Based on the eight manuscript fragments discovered at Qumran and the prevalence of Danielic themes in the New Testament, it is clear that the book(s) of Daniel were widely circulated and had significant influence on early Jewish and Christian literature. Tropes such as the succession of empires and the everlasting dominion of the Most High (Dan. 2 and 7) would become central to later apocalyptic literature such as the book of Revelation, 4 Ezra, and 2 Baruch. Although the court tales have earlier origins likely in the Persian period, the first-person visionary accounts attributed to Daniel date to the persecutions of the Seleucid ruler Antiochus IV Epiphanes (d. 164 BCE). It was also during this time period that the Aramaic and Hebrew traditions underwent their final redaction, culminating in what now resembles the Masoretic text. In the Greek traditions, there remain three additional court-like tales that are otherwise unattested. Although certainty on the matter cannot be established, linguistic features suggest that the tales may not have been originally composed in Greek but rather Hebrew or Aramaic. Each of the three tales—Bel and the Serpent, the tale of Susanna, and the Prayer of Azariah and the Hymn of the Three—relates to the character Daniel, some in more pronounced ways than others. Like the rest of Danielic literature, the date and provenance of these expanded tales are widely debated but they likely emerged during the second century BCE or earlier.

Date Range: 586 BCE - 100 CE

Region: Alexandria and Palestine

Region tags: Israel, Egypt, Jordan, Negev, Judah

Daniel's Greek traditions likely emerged from Alexandria and its Hebrew and Aramaic traditions from Palestine.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

—Source 1: Carol A. Newsom with Brennan W. Breed. Daniel: A Commentary. The Old Testament Library. Louisville: Westminster John Knox Press, 2014.

–Source 2: Anatheia E. Portier-Young. *Apocalypse Against Empire: Theologies of Resistance in Early Judaism*. Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 2011.

–Source 3: John J. Collins. *Daniel: A Commentary on the Book of Daniel*. Hermeneia; Minneapolis, MN: Fortress Press, 1993.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: Parchment

Notes: This answer pertains to the Danielic fragments discovered at Qumran.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field Doesn't Know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field Doesn't Know

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Tomb

– No

Cemetery

– No

Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

Notes: This answer pertains to the Danielic fragments discovered at Qumran.

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– No

↳ Specify

– Specify: Before the fragments discovered at the caves at Qumran, the earliest complete Hebrew and Aramaic versions of Danielic texts were preserved in the Leningrad Codex which dates to the 11th century CE. The earliest attestation of the Old Greek is preserved in fragments of Papyrus 967 which dates to sometime between the 2nd-3rd centuries CE.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The final chapters of MT Daniel (chs. 11-12) mention a group called the "maskilim," which means something like "wise ones" or "skilled ones." And while their role in the transmission of the texts as possible scribes is unclear, they stand in contrast to other groups such as the zealous "hasidim," or "devoted ones," who are mentioned in 1 and 2 Maccabees.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: The concept of canon at the time of MT Daniel's final formation (c. 165 BCE) was not an altogether stable category. Afterwards, however, beginning in the first few centuries CE, Daniel was relegated to the "Writings" (Khetuvim) portion of the Tanakh despite being called a prophet in both the Dead Sea Scrolls (4Q174) and the New Testament (Matt. 24:15).

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Field doesn't know

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: Although the early texts are not accompanied by art, the earliest visual representations of the figure of Daniel in the lion's den are found on mosaics in Rome from the 3rd century CE. Other visual depictions of Danielic themes appear on synagogue floors (Huqoq, 5th century) and Christian sarcophagi (4th century onward).

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unclear whether Danielic texts were used in ritual contexts.

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: The Masoretic text (preserved in Hebrew and Aramaic) is certainly the most well-circulated and dominant but not necessarily more "proper."

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Although passages in Daniel refer to specific lengths of time or dispensations (Dan. 7, 9, and 12), they are not expressly calendrical.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Daniel 12:2 is often cited as describing a "resurrection of the dead," a process of awakening that occurs for both the righteous and the wicked.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: The judgment appears to be perpetual.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: Daniel 7:9-14 describe two high beings: an ancient one (the "ancient of days") and a human-like one (the "son of man").

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: Daniel 2 describes the most high god as "the God of Heaven."

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Daniel 7:4 associates the humanlike one with the rulership of an everlasting kingdom but it is unclear whether he is an earthly monarch or not.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: The kingdom of the most high god is often contrasted with the kingdoms of the earth (see Dan. 2 and 4).

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: Physical descriptions are presumed limited to Daniel 7.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Daniel 2:20-23 depicts a prayer of Daniel that describes the vast knowledge of God which includes the knowledge of times and seasons, as well as the revelation of such details to Daniel.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Divine knowledge of the future, especially the progression of history, is a prevalent theme in Danielic texts but it is unclear to what extent this applies to individuals.

- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
– Specify: N/A

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Yes

Notes: This communication is revelatory and occurs in Danielic literature (Dan. 2, 7, 8, 10, 12) with the assistance of anthropomorphic beings (divine attendants, and/or or supra-humans).

↳ In waking, everyday life
– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams
– Yes

↳ In trance possession
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– Field doesn't know

Notes: Writing as a form of communication (and judgment) between the most high god and the monarch plays a central role in Daniel 5.

Previously human spirits are present
– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The representation of non-human creatures is present (the four hybrid creatures of Dan. 7 and the two domestic animals in Dan. 8) but the extent and reality of the representation is unclear.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: N/A

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

Notes: See above answer of the anthropomorphic supreme being(s).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

Notes: Daniel 8 and 10 are particularly explicit in this regard. The visionary (Daniel) is physically and emotionally affected by the presence of the human-like divine beings who communicate with him.

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

Notes: See above answer on the supreme god's communication with the living.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: See Daniel 7-12.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Prayer, fasting, and proximity to bodies of water are all mentioned as facets of Daniel receiving divine revelation but not explicitly prescribed or guided.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The four hybrid creatures are all judged by the divine court, whereas the fourth creature is punished to the death (Dan. 7). Individual humans experience punishment in the text—such as the courtiers who conspire against Daniel who are burned in the fiery furnace and consumed by the lions—but it is not clear if this is meted out directly by supernatural beings.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although not explicitly framed as such within the text, the figure of the human-like one (the "son of man") in Dan. 7 is later interpreted as a messianic-type figure in a number of Jewish texts including 1 Enoch. The title "Son of Man" in Daniel 7 is also interpreted as foretelling Jesus of Nazareth and appears throughout the Gospels of the Christian New Testament.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ At specified time in future

– Yes

At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Worship of the most high god may indirectly be one of the primary values of the text.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: Daniel does abstain from the king's food in Dan. 1, and combines fasting and mourning in Dan. 10.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: The author(s) or community that redacted the final versions of Danielic texts were likely of scribal association and may have seen themselves as a type of "elect" group. Daniel 12 refers to a group called the "maskilim," which means "wise ones" or "skilled ones," and may point to the group who assembled and redacted the final version of the MT.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There do not appear to be formal educational institutions apart from Daniel's "education" in the Babylonian imperial court in Daniel 1.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

Is education gendered according to the text?

– Yes

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: Daniel 7-12 describe a number of conflicts between empires as well as in heavenly arenas. In particular, Daniel 11 is concerned with presenting an account of Hellenistic history from Alexander up until the time of Antiochus IV Epiphanes including the accounts of specific battles and successions which are framed as a prophetic revelation through an angelic mediator.

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?
– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?
– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No